

ON THE TIME VARIATION OF FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICAL CONSTANTS

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TIME VARIATION OF FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS

The term physical constant expresses the notion of a physical quantity subject to experimental measurement which is independent of the time or location of the experiment. The immutability of these fundamental constants is an important cornerstone of the laws of physics as currently known. Paul Dirac in 1937 speculated that physical constants might be subject to change over time in proportion of the age of the universe ^[1]. In a previous contribution ^[2], we derived coefficients, the conversion factors, expressed in units of $\alpha \approx 1/137$ ^[3], where α is the fine-structure constant; α can therefore be expressed as the ratio of the theoretical radius of the observable universe $R_{uT} \approx 13.6\text{-}13.8$ Gly, to the measured radius $R_{uI} \approx 46.5$ Gly ^[4]:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{R_{uT}}{R_{uI}}\right)^4 \approx \left(\frac{13.6 \text{ Gly}}{46.5 \text{ Gly}}\right)^4 \approx \frac{1}{137} \quad (1.1)$$

Since α can be expressed via equation (1.1), unless there was a corresponding variation in the speed of light c , its value must have been different. By using the theoretical and real radii that the universe had at a certain period in the past, it is possible to derive the values of α , which tend to 1 as the universe approaches the singularity of the Big Bang. Finally, since all other conversion factors are expressed in terms of α , this means that all other constants and quantities also had different values in the past (and so in the future). This implies that physical laws have not remained unchanged throughout the history of the universe. Regarding the spatial variation of α , the issue is more complex and falls outside the scope of this work.

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